

Thermodynamics of molecular association of biomolecules with iodine : A study of molecular complex formation

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Abstract : Studies, on donor-acceptor systems in acetone solutions at 30, 40 and 50 °C with a precision of ± 0.1 °C have been made using a calibrated pyknometer and viscometer. Two series of biomolecules viz. adenine, adenosine and adenosine-5-phosphate and guanine, guanosine and guanosine-5-phosphate have been chosen as donors while iodine has been selected as an acceptor for the present studies. Thermodynamic functions viz. ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^* have been calculated to interpret the mechanism of association and solvation of 1 : 1 molecular complex. Coefficient and constant of Vand's equation have been evaluated to support the molecular interactions.

Keywords : Molecular association, molecular interaction, donor-acceptor, charge transfer complex, thermodynamic parameters.

Introduction

Purine and pyrimidine bases¹ are very important from the structural and biological point of view because they are the main building blocks of nucleic acids. The charge-transfer complex formation plays a major role in the pharmacological action of biomolecules and non-metallic substrates e.g. iodine. Saksena and co-workers have determined the conformation² of molecular complex between a neuroleptic drug and iodine. UV spectra and thermodynamic³ parameters support the mechanism of formation of NO-bond, 1 : 1 molecular complex which predominates over all other unstable structures. Ultrasonic studies⁴⁻⁶ made on donor-acceptor systems reported earlier present the hydrodynamic behaviour of molecular aggregates in the solvation sphere.

Relative viscosity measurements have been made in the present studies to study macroscopic relaxation process which leads to the adjustment of the molecular complex in solution.

Results and discussion

In our previous paper⁶, a non-linear variation of changes in adiabatic compressibility, $\Delta\beta_s$ with the mole fraction has been discussed in the light of UV spectra. In another communication⁷ a 1 : 1 NO-Bond model has been assigned based on studies on molecular interaction parameters. A dipole moment of 23.6 D for a purine-I₂

complex has been calculated predicting that two end dipoles are held by van der Waals forces. Due to molecular collisions with the solvent molecules, the molecular complex becomes ionic in nature. Due to low concentration of I⁻, I₃⁻ and CTC, only [D : I]⁺ structure predominates over all other unstable structures. Ion pairs viz. (D⁺ : I⁻) or (D⁻ : I⁺) are found in very low concentrations and can be neglected in proposing a mechanism for the molecular association.

These results are similar in the case of amino acids with iodine in water⁸ and in aqueous solutions of purines and pyrimidines with iodine⁹. In the case of nucleotides possible cleavage of phosphate site can lead to uncertain values of thermodynamic functions. Although it is very difficult to predict the final mechanism of association in a non-aqueous solvent yet a three step process can be proposed.

The possibility of self association is excluded due to very low concentration of donors¹⁰. The relative viscosity has been interpreted on the basis of viscosity coefficients B and D by the rate process theory^{11,12} and regular

Table 1. Densities and viscosities for the systems, at different temperatures

Sl. no.	$C \times 10^3$ (mol L ⁻¹)	303 K		313 K		323 K	
		d (g ml ⁻¹)	η (c.poise)	d (g ml ⁻¹)	η (c.poise)	d (g ml ⁻¹)	η (c.poise)
System I							
1.	0.3460	0.7813	0.3518	0.7810	0.3132	0.7796	0.2870
2.	0.3820	0.7823	0.3546	0.7817	0.3248	0.7801	0.2974
3.	0.4360	0.7842	0.3679	0.7827	0.3363	0.7812	0.3105
4.	0.4720	0.7856	0.3768	0.7836	0.3477	0.7820	0.3172
5.	0.4900	0.7868	0.3856	0.7842	0.3535	0.7824	0.3237
System II							
1.	0.3460	0.7820	0.3463	0.7812	0.3020	0.7796	0.3039
2.	0.3820	0.7838	0.3595	0.7818	0.3079	0.7802	0.3106
3.	0.4360	0.7856	0.3768	0.7830	0.3253	0.7812	0.3238
4.	0.4720	0.7868	0.3856	0.7838	0.3367	0.7820	0.3304
5.	0.4900	0.7870	0.3939	0.7845	0.3246	0.7824	0.3368
System III							
1.	0.3460	0.7826	0.3507	0.7814	0.3134	0.7809	0.3040
2.	0.3820	0.7831	0.3633	0.7820	0.3192	0.7816	0.3107
3.	0.4360	0.7856	0.3891	0.7836	0.3367	0.7828	0.3364
4.	0.4720	0.7872	0.3981	0.7844	0.3481	0.7836	0.3492
5.	0.4900	0.7892	0.4073	0.7849	0.3538	0.7840	0.3556
System IV							
1.	0.3460	0.7801	0.3330	0.7714	0.3038	0.7610	0.2775
2.	0.3820	0.7814	0.3501	0.7724	0.3098	0.7624	0.2843
3.	0.4360	0.7862	0.3647	0.7764	0.3225	0.7690	0.3060
4.	0.4720	0.7892	0.3444	0.7801	0.3352	0.7708	0.3127
5.	0.4900	0.7901	0.3789	0.7804	0.3408	0.7716	0.3192
System V							
1.	0.3460	0.7805	0.3415	0.7731	0.3045	0.7612	0.2775
2.	0.3820	0.7821	0.3546	0.7741	0.3104	0.7658	0.2855
3.	0.4360	0.7884	0.3740	0.7783	0.3295	0.7728	0.3197
4.	0.4720	0.7925	0.3884	0.7801	0.3352	0.7745	0.3266
5.	0.4900	0.7957	0.3941	0.7804	0.3408	0.7758	0.3334
System VI							
1.	0.3460	0.7809	0.3499	0.7748	0.3107	0.7616	0.2903
2.	0.3820	0.7828	0.3672	0.7784	0.3233	0.7666	0.3047
3.	0.4360	0.7872	0.3867	0.7796	0.3045	0.7744	0.3266
4.	0.4720	0.7938	0.4096	0.7806	0.3519	0.7752	0.3331
5.	0.4900	0.7968	0.4235	0.7808	0.3619	0.7762	0.3390

solution theory^{13,14}. Srivastava¹⁵ in his classical paper has presented relationships between excess properties and thermodynamic parameters for binary and ternary systems. Only a little has been described by Williamson in his monograph¹⁶ about non-electrolyte solutions and thermodynamic functions¹⁷.

Since, the flow of a liquid is a rate process¹⁸, we can

safely use the Eyring's equation to determine the free energy changes by applying the theory of absolute reaction rate to the problem of viscosity i.e.

$$\eta = \frac{hN}{V} .e^{\Delta G^*/RT} \quad (1)$$

Free energy of activation, ΔG^* for the viscous flow is

given by

$$\Delta G^* = RT \ln \eta V/hN \quad (2)$$

where h is Planck's constant and N is Avogadro's number. V is the volume of one mole of solution particles and is given by the relation,

$$V = \frac{1000}{n_1 + \nu n_2} \text{ cm}^3 \quad (3)$$

where ν is the number of species into which the solute molecule dissociates.

In the case of association ν is unity and n_2 is the number of moles of solvent, n_1 per litre of solution is given by,

$$n_1 = \frac{1000d - n_2\bar{M}}{M_0} \quad (4)$$

where M_0 and \bar{M} are the molecular weights of the solvent and solute respectively. (When there are two solutes \bar{M} is taken as $\bar{M} = M_1X_1 + M_2X_2$; M_1 molecular weight of donor and M_2 of acceptor).

From the Gibbs-Helmholtz equation, ΔG^* is related to change in standard enthalpy, ΔH^* and change in standard entropy, ΔS^* as follows :

$$\Delta G^* = \Delta H^* - T\Delta S^* \quad (5)$$

By definition,

$$\Delta S^* = -d/dT (\Delta G^*) \quad (5a)$$

$$\text{or } = -d/dT (RT \ln \eta V/hN)$$

$$\text{or } = -R(T.d/dT (\ln \eta V/hN) + 1.\ln \eta V/hN)$$

$$\text{or } = -R(T.\text{slope} + \ln \eta V/hN) \quad (6)$$

The slope $d/dT (\ln \eta V/hN)$ is determined by the method of least squares for the plot of $\ln \eta V/hN$ vs T and, in turn, ΔS^* and ΔH^* are obtained by using eqs. (5) and (5a). The thermodynamic functions i.e. ΔG^* , ΔH^* , ΔS^* are reported in Table 2 for all six systems.

The relative viscosity, η_r can be fitted in the Vand's equation¹⁹ for spherical particles as follows :

$$\ln \eta/\eta_0 = \frac{2.5\phi}{1 - K\phi} \quad (7)$$

where $\phi = c\bar{V}$ is volume fraction, η_0 viscosity of solvent, and $\eta_r = \eta/\eta_0$ relative viscosity and C is the molar concentration. After rearrangement, we get

$$\frac{C}{\log \eta_r} = \frac{2.303}{25\bar{V}} - \frac{2.303}{2.5} KC \quad (8)$$

where K is the generalized particle interaction coefficient

Table 2. ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^* for the system at different temperatures

Sl. no.	$C \times 10^3$ (mol L ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kcal mol ⁻¹)			ΔH^* (kcal mol ⁻¹)			ΔS^* (cal deg ⁻¹)		
		303 K	313 K	323 K	303 K	313 K	323 K	303 K	313 K	323 K
System I										
1.	0.346	15.41	16.13	16.66	2.17	2.66	2.91	-43.69	-43.03	-42.57
2.	0.382	15.78	16.22	16.68	1.97	2.10	2.24	-45.58	-45.10	-44.72
3.	0.436	15.81	16.25	16.72	1.94	1.96	2.10	-45.78	-45.65	-45.27
4.	0.472	15.79	16.27	16.73	1.87	2.03	2.27	-45.96	-45.50	-44.77
5.	0.490	15.80	16.28	16.74	1.93	2.09	2.22	-45.78	-45.35	-44.96
System II										
1.	0.346	15.74	16.16	16.70	1.17	1.24	1.34	-48.08	-47.68	-47.57
2.	0.382	15.76	16.19	16.72	1.29	1.38	1.47	-47.77	-47.33	-47.21
3.	0.436	15.79	16.22	16.74	1.36	1.46	1.55	-47.62	-47.17	-47.02
4.	0.472	15.81	16.24	16.76	1.37	1.41	1.56	-47.65	-47.39	-47.06
5.	0.490	15.82	16.25	16.76	1.39	1.47	1.51	-47.63	-47.21	-47.03
System III										
1.	0.346	15.75	16.20	16.70	0.21	0.23	0.24	-51.28	-51.04	-50.91
2.	0.382	15.77	16.21	16.72	1.42	1.52	1.63	-47.35	-46.94	-46.74
3.	0.436	15.81	16.25	16.76	1.31	1.40	1.49	-47.84	-47.44	-47.29
4.	0.472	15.83	16.27	16.79	1.16	1.21	1.32	-48.41	-48.11	-47.90
5.	0.490	15.84	16.28	16.80	1.23	1.23	1.40	-48.20	-48.07	-47.67

Table-2 (contd.)

System IV										
1.	0.346	15.72	16.19	16.65	1.46	1.56	1.66	-47.06	-46.74	-46.43
2.	0.382	15.74	16.20	16.67	1.47	1.56	1.66	-47.11	-46.78	-46.47
3.	0.436	15.77	16.22	16.71	1.46	1.56	1.66	-47.23	-46.85	-46.59
4.	0.472	15.79	16.25	16.72	1.47	1.57	1.66	-47.27	-46.92	-46.64
5.	0.490	15.79	16.26	16.74	1.36	1.46	1.56	-47.61	-47.27	-47.01
System V										
1.	0.346	15.74	16.19	16.65	1.69	1.80	1.92	-46.36	-45.96	-45.62
2.	0.382	15.76	16.20	16.67	1.81	1.86	1.98	-46.05	-45.81	-45.47
3.	0.436	15.78	16.23	16.74	1.25	1.29	1.42	-47.96	-47.74	-47.42
4.	0.472	15.81	16.25	16.75	1.36	1.44	1.53	-47.71	-47.31	-47.12
5.	0.490	15.82	16.26	16.76	1.34	1.42	1.51	-47.80	-47.40	-47.22
System VI										
1.	0.346	15.75	16.20	16.68	1.18	1.23	1.31	-48.09	-47.81	-47.58
2.	0.382	15.78	16.22	16.71	1.52	1.62	1.72	-47.06	-46.65	-46.40
3.	0.436	15.81	16.25	16.75	1.41	1.50	1.60	-47.53	-47.14	-45.92
4.	0.472	15.83	16.27	16.76	1.70	1.82	1.94	-46.63	-46.17	-45.89
5.	0.490	15.85	16.29	16.77	1.82	1.94	2.07	-46.31	-45.84	-45.52

Error in ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^* $\sim 0.1\%$, where $30^\circ\text{C} = 303\text{ K}$, $40^\circ\text{C} = 313\text{ K}$, $50^\circ\text{C} = 323\text{ K}$, $R = 1.987\text{ cal deg.}^{-1}\text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $h\nu = 1.58 \times 6.023 \times 10^{-1}\text{ cal mol}^{-1}$.

(Out of the nine systems studied, values of thermodynamic parameters for five systems have been included).

and \bar{V} is the effective flowing volume. K has been used for studying hydrodynamic interactions by other workers but the concept has been extended to study weaker interactions in electrolyte and non-electrolyte systems²⁰⁻²² under limited concentration range. \bar{V} has been evaluated from the intercept of plot of $C[\log \eta_r]^{-1}$ vs C after extrapolation to infinite dilution. Its units are $\text{cm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}$. The intercept and slope have been calculated on a computer using a standard package programme written in BASIC for the linear regression analysis. Comparison of \bar{V} and K for all systems at 303, 313 and 323 K is shown in Table 3. Due to manual measurements and limitation of weather conditions, experimental work has been done only at three temperatures.

Thermodynamic functions reported in Table 2 show a regular trend of increase with temperature. It is clear that ΔH^* is of the order of 1-2 kcal mol^{-1} which is less than required for H-bonding²³. Recently thermodynamic interaction parameters²⁴ for some binary mixtures (non polar systems) have been interpreted in terms of statistical mechanical theory²⁵, which directly correlates the thermodynamic (macro) quantities with the molecular structure (micro) without any assumption. Increase in ΔS^* with temperature indicates increase in repulsion energy between donor and acceptor molecules.

In the present studies there is only a possibility of

Table 3. \bar{V} and K for the Systems I to VI

Sys-tem	$\bar{V} \times 10^2 (\text{cm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1})$			K		
	303 K	313 K	323 K	303 K	313 K	323 K
I	-1.83	-1.41	-1.83	26.57	17.95	33.00
II	-3.04	-0.89	-0.79	50.74	8.06	7.59
III	-1.61	-1.16	-0.75	22.12	15.92	7.82
IV	-2.69	-2.82	-1.11	41.92	45.73	13.29
V	-4.70	-2.22	-1.01	88.92	33.44	12.29
VI	-1.64	-1.69	-0.90	24.85	25.13	11.48

charge transfer interactions or collisional complex formation between donor and acceptor molecules. The negative values of effective flowing volume \bar{V} , shows lesser role of solvent in molecular association. Decrease in hydrodynamic interactions are shown by the decrease in the values of K with the increase in temperature.

Experimental

Acetone, A.R. (BDH) has been redistilled in a quick fit vertical column and kept in a desiccator before use. Adenine and guanine are GR grade procured from Koch-Light Laboratories and adenosine and guanosine are AnalaR grade from BDH whereas the adenosine-5-phosphate and guanosine-5-phosphate have been obtained from s.d. fine Chem., Bombay.

All the compounds have been used as such except that nucleotides have been purified by preparing saturated solution in 50% water and ethanol mixture. Purity of samples has been checked by determination of m.p's.

A double stem pycnometer has been used to determine density of solvent and solutions at a constant temperature in a NBE type Ultrathermostat.

Uncertainty in density, d is the order of 0.01%. The procedure of calibration has already been described in our previous publication². An improved Ostwald type viscometer with a water circulation jacket has been used to determine viscosity of solvent and solutions. The calibration constants a and b of viscometer have been determined at 303, 313 and 323 K and detailed procedure is described in our paper⁵. Uncertainty in viscosity, η is nearly 0.01%. Fresh donor acceptor solutions in acetone have been prepared by the variation of initial solution of donors ($\sim 10^{-3} M$) and acceptor ($\sim 10^{-4} M$) keeping the total volume constant in 50 ml volumetric flasks.

Systems studied are as follows : (a) adenine + iodine + acetone; (b) adenosine + iodine + acetone; (c) adenosine-5-phosphate + iodine + acetone; (d) guanine + iodine + acetone; (e) guanosine + iodine + acetone; (f) guanosine-5-phosphate + iodine + acetone.

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